

Studies in Quinoline Compounds. Part III.

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The fact that certain derivatives of quinoline ("plasmochin") and certain arsenicals possess antimalarial properties, led us to synthesise some arsenic derivatives of quinoline. The first idea that would strike a worker in this direction is to attempt to introduce arsenic directly into the quinoline nucleus. Up till now, such a method has not been found feasible except in the case of quinaldine (Frankel and Lowy, *Ber.*, 1913, **46**, 2549). The compound has been obtained indirectly by the application of Döbner—Miller's reaction to *p*-aminophenylarsonic acid.

With the view of introducing arsenic directly into derivatives of quinoline we first tried the method of Bart (German Patent, 250264) as well as Mouneyrat's modification of it (British Patent, 142947). In all our attempts we obtained dyes and reduction products only. No compound containing arsenic was isolated during a prolonged investigation in this direction.

We next tried the mercuric acetate method, but here we found that during the course of the reaction the mercury was almost quantitatively reduced to the metallic state.

Subsequently we tried to condense aminoquinolines with aromatic arsenicals. With this object, chloroacetyl-*p*-arsanilic acid was condensed with various aminoquinolines, following the method of Jacobs and Heidelberger (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, **41**, 1810). The compounds enumerated below were thereby obtained:—

- (1) Quinoline-8-aminoacetyl-*p*-arsanilic acid.
- (2) 6-Methoxyquinoline-5-aminoacetyl-*p*-arsanilic acid.
- (3) Quinoline-6-aminoacetyl-*p*-arsanilic acid.
- (4) 2-Methylquinoline-6-aminoacetyl-*p*-arsanilic acid.

These compounds are generally yellow in colour. They are insoluble in water, very sparingly soluble in common organic

solvents such as alcohol, ether, acetone, etc. They however dissolve very easily in aqueous caustic alkalis. From the alkaline solutions, acids precipitate the original compound. Continued boiling with dilute alkali causes hydrolysis. They are sparingly soluble in dilute mineral acids.

On treating with an excess of sodium nitrite solution in 50% acetic acid suspension beautiful crystalline nitroso-derivatives are obtained.

For the sake of examining the therapeutic properties we also prepared arsanilic acid salts of 8- and 6-aminoquinolines.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Quinoline-8-aminoacetyl-p-arsanilic Acid.

Chloroacetylarsanilic acid (2.26 g.), prepared according to Jacob and Heidelberger's method (*loc. cit.*), is dissolved in *N*-sodium hydroxide solution (7.5 c.c.) and to it is added 8-aminoquinoline (1.6 g. in 7.5 c.c. alcohol). This mixture is then boiled on a water-bath for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. The solid which separates out is collected, washed with very dilute hydrochloric acid and then with water. It is then dried in vacuum. The compound has a deep yellow colour. It dissolves very easily in aqueous alkalis, diethylamine and also in concentrated hydrochloric acid. It is very difficultly soluble in all other solvents; m. p. 171° (decomp.). (Found: N, 10.2; As, 18.2. $C_{17}H_{16}O_4N_3As$ requires N, 10.5; As, 18.7 per cent.).

The *sodium salt* of the above compound is prepared by dissolving the moist acid in the smallest quantity of *N*-sodium hydroxide and then precipitating with an excess of alcohol. It is very easily soluble in water.

The *nitroso-derivative* is prepared by suspending 1 g. of the acid in 10 c.c. of 50% acetic acid and then treating with a solution of 1 g. of sodium nitrite. On scratching the solution, the nitroso-compound separates. It has got a greenish-yellow colour. It

decomposes with effervescence at about 182°. (Found: N, 12·8. $C_{17}H_{15}O_5N_4As$ requires N, 13·00 per cent.).

6-Methoxyquinoline-5-aminoacetyl-p-arsanilic Acid.

The compound is prepared from 6-methoxy-5-aminoquinoline and chloroacetyl-p-arsanilic acid, the procedure being the same as in the case of the above compound. It has a dirty grey colour. It is easily soluble in alkalis but sparingly in all other solvents. It does not melt even at 240°. (Found: N, 9·5. $C_{18}H_{18}O_5N_3As$ requires N, 9·7 per cent.).

The *sodium salt*, prepared as indicated above, is very easily soluble in water.

The *nitroso-derivative* is an almost white substance and does not melt at 240°. (Found: N, 12·1. $C_{18}H_{17}O_6N_4As$ requires N, 12·2 per cent.).

Quinoline-6-aminoacetyl-p-arsanilic Acid.

This compound is prepared from 6-aminoquinoline and chloroacetylarsanilic acid in the usual manner.

It is a greenish-yellow powder, easily soluble in caustic alkalis, but practically insoluble in all organic solvents. It does not melt at 240°. (Found: N, 10·3. $C_{17}H_{16}O_4N_3As$ requires N, 10·5 per cent.). The *sodium salt* is prepared by dissolving the free acid in the smallest amount of dilute sodium hydroxide and then precipitating with alcohol. It is very easily soluble in water.

The *nitroso-derivative* melts above 240°. (Found: N, 12·7. $C_{17}H_{15}O_5N_4As$ requires N, 13·0 per cent.).

2-Methylquinoline-6-aminoacetyl-p-arsanilic Acid.

It is obtained from 2-methyl-6-aminoquinoline and chloroacetyl-p-arsanilic acid. In its properties it resembles the other compounds of the series. It does not soften below 240°. (Found: N, 9·7. $C_{18}H_{18}O_4N_3As$ requires N, 10·1 per cent.). The *sodium salt* prepared as usual is very easily soluble in water.

8-Aminoquinoline p-arsanilate.—This salt is prepared by mixing aqueous solutions of equimolecular quantities of 8-aminoquinoline hydrochloride and atoxyl. It separates out on scratching for some time. It is somewhat soluble in water. The compound decomposes

after a few days. It begins to soften from 210° but does not melt clearly at 240° .

6-Aminoquinoline-p-arsanilate.—This compound is similarly prepared from 6-aminoquinoline hydrochloride and atoxyl. It does not melt at 240° .

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